

THE PROBLEM OF TRANSLATING HISTORICAL REALITIES OF UZBEK LANGUAGE INTO ENGLISH

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Annotation: *This article presents the brief history and evolution of Translation Studies from Uzbek into English. It also provides some possible lexical problems in translation between Uzbek and English, and how to deal with them. It gives examples of such problems in translation and considers how to solve them. The article also discusses the problem of a lack of equivalence in translation, which results in lexical gaps at the semantic field level. It also learns the translation problems of phraseological and stylistic units as well as grammatical ones. The translation problems will be expressed with the help of the examples taken from the works of Utkir Khoshimov who was one of the most prominent writers of Uzbek literary world.*

Keywords: *lexical problems, grammatical and stylistic problems of translation literary translation, cultural problems of the text.*

INTRODUCTION

Translation has been formed in the culture and history of the peoples of the world for many years and is one of the types of creative activities that has been developing over the years. By translating a concept or phrase from one language into another, people exchange ideas and learn about other people's cultures, customs, and traditions. Through translation, economic, political and cultural cooperation has been established amongst the countries of the world. This, in turn, paved the way for the comprehensive development of states. That is why translation and interpretation are so important in the language industry today¹.

Also, translation plays a significant role not only in teaching and learning processes of language education, but also it is very important to convey the one's mentality, customs and traditions which exist in their cultures. Therefore, there is a great amount of necessity for different types of translation studies. Knowing how the translations works can help learners to compare and understand different aspects of the different nations and cultures. Since you are required to understand and know, easily follow the meaning of the given text or contexts while you are learning a foreign language. Interestingly, when you begin to investigate a culture or deal with any foreign language learning, you will definitely have to work with the texts and literary

¹ Abduazizov, M. Kholbekov. Well-known theorist of translation // Literature and art of Uzbekistan, December 14, 2012.

resources. As a result of that, most of translators and language providers need to face some challenges which can be real obstacles for readers and learners of the language which is being learned or taught. Moreover, the translated forms of materials or resources for investigation, assist to express and understand the meaning of the texts and literary works².

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Generally, a good translation is not easily or directly translated into another language and in this process, it is required from a translator to use appropriate methods and approaches to keep the real meaning of the texts. Laconically, we may articulate that “translation” is a text-processing and text-reproducing activity which comes from a source text to a resulting text. Other types of text-processing and text-reproducing activities are commenting the text, summarizing text, interpreting the meaning of the work, adapting a text for a different group of addressees, transposing the text into another medium, etc. What kind of translation from all these text-processing activities is that translation is based on an act of creating a relation of equivalence between a source text in one language and its cognition and translation in another language...? The German translator, Wolfram Wilss (2018,2) gave and offered a good explanation and definition to translation, according to his idea that *“Translation is a text-processing and text-re-verbalisation process which leads from a source text to a target text that is as equivalent as possible and presupposes an understanding of the original text in terms of content and style. Translating is a process, which consists of two main phases. One of them is a phase of text comprehension in which the translator analyses the source language text with reference to its meaning and style. The following one is a phase of linguistic reconstruction, in which the translator reproduces the source language text which he had analysed in terms of content and style, under optimal consideration of communicative equivalence”* (2,18).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Therefore, it is often said that keeping national-coloured words should be used but not so frequently. What was meant by that? If you deal with translation studies, everyone should be aware of the translation problems that are related not only linguistic sphere but also non-linguistic sphere too. Because while translating the texts, you should take into consideration of the cultural aspects of the words, expressions and sentences that are being translated into another language. As far as the things that motivate to write this topic are concerned, we will enumerate some of them as forethought of the initial points to write this research³.

Granted, this research is one of the new topical approaches which has not been learned yet by the majority of scholars, translators and linguists in Uzbekistan. Furthermore, these are going to be almost new translation problems from the Uzbek

² Muminov O. M., Turgunov R. Written translation. - T., 2018.

³ Rahimov G`. Theory and practice of translation. - Tashkent: “National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan” State Scientific Publishing House, 2016.

language into the English language. In addition to this, one advantage of this kind of dissertation topics is that it will really help learners and readers in both Uzbek and English languages understand the feelings, the ways of life, and character of the nation. By doing this research, we will be able to not only achieve to translate cultural-valued books but by courtesy of being translated into English, it will assist learners to see the rich literary heritage to the whole world and in the meanwhile, it will also support other nations to know more about Uzbekistan and its culture. So, it is also acknowledged as a source of strengthening the knowledge according to "Anthropocentrism" in linguistic fields such as Translation Studies, Language Learning and Discourse analysis.

Translation has always evolved in close connection with literature. The introduction of examples of world literature into the cultural life of nations through translation has helped one nation to get acquainted with the spiritual life and customs of another nation. The role of translation is invaluable in bringing world literature into our lives and bringing peoples closer together.

The first English translations of Uzbek literature are, of course, associated with the name of Alisher Navoi. The great thinker's epic "Lyson ut-tayr" was translated into English by E. Fitzgerald and published in 1899 in Boston, USA. The prose description of the same work was translated into English by Canadian translator Harry Dick in collaboration with Uzbek translator N. Kambarov. "Muhokamat ul-lug'atayn" by Alisher Navoiy was translated into English by Robert Deverux in 1966 in the United States, and the great poet's epic "Sab'ai Sayyar" was translated into English by American professor W. Firman. In 1988, the Vatan Society of Uzbekistan published Alisher Navoi's proverbs in Latin translation by Margaret Bettlin. The English collection "Uzbekistan speaks", published in Tashkent in 1961, includes samples of ghazals, rubais, proverbs of Alisher Navoi and an excerpt from the epic "Farhod and Shirin".

One of the first translations into English was "Temur's Statutes", which can be considered a documentary, historical, artistic, autobiographical work in the genre of Amir Temur. One of the famous writers of Uzbekistan Pirmkul Kadyrov in his article "The role of Temur's rules "in the history of our spirituality" thinks about this, and emphasizes that it should be read as a heroic epic written in the Turkic language. and the extreme darkness of meaning is reminiscent of the epic Alp Er Tonga and the history of Bilga Hakan and Kultegin in stone inscriptions. The small size of the work suggests that its meaning does not fit into some multi-volume novels. "... For six centuries," the author writes, "Temur's Statutes" deserve to be among the leading historical, literary and linguistic monuments that have appeared on the soil of Uzbekistan. "It should be highly valued in Uzbek literature as an autobiographical work that started realism six centuries ago and should be included in school textbooks."

CONCLUSION

To sum up, we can say that in word-for-word, literary translation or semantic

ones, translators are required not only to have a huge vocabulary skill but also to understand the culture and traditions of Uzbekistan. Moreover, looking at the specific problems and challenges of translation of stylistic devices, or other lexical problems of the translation, means and methods which are used to have translated and also having information of the history of literary translation from Uzbek into English, we can assume that majority of them in most cases depends on the culture of the language. By looking through the observation of the translation, we can say that translation from Uzbek into English or other foreign languages quite differs due to specific features and peculiarities of those languages. Moreover, it is obvious that the translation process requires exact and adequate performance of contents, in the meanwhile a translator is required to have not only the language skills but also, he or she must have a broad knowledge of cultural diversity, specific vocabulary and understanding of both national and international world pictures.

REFERENCES:

1. Abduazizov, M. Kholbekov. Well-known theorist of translation // Literature and art of Uzbekistan, December 14, 2012.
2. Esenboev R. The art of translation. 1,2,3,4 books. Tashkent. 2016.
3. Kamilov N. Traditions of our translation. Sharq Yulduz magazine. 2018, 8-son.
4. Muminov O. M., Turgunov R. Written translation. - T., 2018.
5. Musayev KM Literary translation and speech culture. - T., 2016
6. Musayev KM Fundamentals of translation theory. Textbook. - T.: "Fan" publishing house of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2015. - 352 p.
7. Rahimov G`. Theory and practice of translation. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2016.
8. Rahimov G`. Typology of English speech. - Samarkand: SamDChTI edition, 2018.